

FARCLIMATE

DELIVERABLE D1.2 Initial Data Management Plan

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List of acronyms

AAM: Autor Accepted Manuscript

CC: Creative Commons

CORDIS: Community Research and Development Information Service

DMP: Data Management Plan

FAIR: Findable, Accessible, Interoperable and Reusable

GDPR: General Data Protection Regulation

IPR: Intellectual Property Rights

NACE: Nomenclature of Economic Activities (*Nomenclature statistique des Activités économiques dans la Communauté Européenne*)

OA: Open Access

OECD: Organization for Economic Co-operation and Development

PC: Project coordinator

UNESCO: United Nations Educational, Scientific and Cultural Organization

WP: Work Package

Project information

Project full title: Moving ForwARd to achieving CLIMATE-resilient and sustainable European regional economic systems - FARCLIMATE

Acronym: FARCLIMATE

Call: HORIZON-MISS-2022-CLIMA-01

Topic: HORIZON-MISS-2022-CLIMA-01-04 - Transformation of regional economic systems for climate resilience and sustainability

Start date: 1st October 2023

Duration: 48 months

List of participants:

Partner No.	Organisation Name Acronym
1 (Coord.)	UNIVERSIDAD DE VIGO UVIGO
2	CONTACTICA S.L. CTA
3	INTERNATIONAL UNION FOR CONSERVATION OF NATURE UICN
4	C4G - CONSULTING AND TRAINING NETWORK, LDA C4G
5	INVIABLE LIFE CYCLE THINKING S.L. INV
6	MUNICIPIO DO FUNDAO FUNDAO
7	GREEN GROWTH GENERATION GGG
8	UNIVERSITY OF LIEGE ULIEGE
9	FUNDACIÓN CENTRO DE SERVICIOS Y PROMOCIÓN FORESTAL Y DE SU INDUSTRIA DE CASTILLA Y LEÓN CESEFOR
10	UNIVERSIDADE NOVA DE LISBOA UNL
11	FUNDACIÓN PARA LA PESCA Y MARISQUEO FUNDAMAR FUNDAMAR
12	EUROPEAN NETWORK OF LIVING LABS IVZW ENoLL
13	ETHNIKO KENTRO EREVNAS KAI TECHNOLOGIKIS ANAPTYXIS CERTH
14	LAUREA-AMMATTIKORKEAKOULU OY LAU

Deliverable details

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Abstract:	This document provides the initial version of the Data Management Plan. This deliverable includes the procedure to manage the data in the project, following the FAIR principles. This plan will be updated at appropriate intervals to reflect important changes due to the inclusion of new datasets, changes in consortium policies or any other external factors. A final version of the Data Management Plan will be released by the end of the project.

Version	Date	Description
Draft_V0.1	25/03/2024	First draft
Version_V1.0	08/04/2024	Initial version

1 Executive summary

This document presents the **initial version of the Data Management Plan, outlining the procedures for managing project data.**

FARCLIMATE partners will ensure that all the collected data and research outputs are in accordance with the **FAIR principles** (Findable, Accessible, Interoperable and Reusable) and are compliant with open access, ethical and legal requirements, intellectual property rights and information security.

This plan will be updated at appropriate intervals to reflect important changes due to the inclusion of new datasets, changes in consortium policies or any other external factors. A final version of the Data Management Plan will be released by the end of the project (M48).

Section 2 elaborates on the general strategy for data management, including principles and legislation, as well as general procedures for ensuring data FAIR alongside considerations for data security and data management responsibilities. Zenodo, a free and open-access repository jointly developed by OpenAIRE and CERN, is highlighted as the preferred platform for depositing open data within FARCLIMATE, facilitating researchers to deposit, share, and preserve a wide array of research outputs across different formats.

The subsequent sections delve into the specifics of different types of data, documents, publications and other research outputs suitable to FAIR principles. Namely:

- Internal project data and documentation (Section 3).
- Internal data and documentation with personal and sensitive information (Section 4).
- Reused datasets and information (Section 5).
- Datasets for open publication (Section 6).
- Research publications (Section 7).
- Other information and documents with reuse value (Section 8).
- Online sites (Section 9).

2 General plan for data management

FARCLIMATE activities involve collecting and generating quantitative and qualitative data, or a combination of both. This data will be used from various perspectives, using different methodological approaches for different purposes such as research, innovation and community-building.

In this deliverable, we establish the initial data management plan (DMP). This DMP also includes some data management considerations for other research outputs, such as the Training platform (WP4) and the Transformation Hub (WP7). This DMP will be updated at appropriate intervals in the Periodic Reports to the EC, and a final version of the DMP (D1.3) will be released by M48.

FARCLIMATE partners will ensure that all the collected data and research outputs are in accordance with the following principles:

- **FAIR principles** (Findable, Accessible, Interoperable and Reusable), following the template established in *EU Grants: Data management plan (HE): V1.1*.
- Research outputs '**as open as possible, as closed as necessary**'.

FARCLIMATE will ensure **compliance with open access, ethical and legal requirements, intellectual property rights and information security**. The project will adhere to all applicable European and national laws and regulations, including additional regulations that may be implemented during the project's development. We highlight the following legislation:

- **Directive (EU) 2019/1024** (Open data and the re-use of public sector information).
- Sect. 6-8 of **Annex 5 of the Grant Agreement**.
- Art. 19 of the **Regulation (EU) 2021/695** (Horizon Europe), which states the principle of proportionality and the rights to privacy, protection of personal data, physical and mental integrity, non-discrimination and assurance of human health protection.
- **Regulation (EU) 2016/679** (General Data Protection Regulation, GDPR).

FARCLIMATE partners will deposit data in an open online research data repository to ensure early and open sharing and reproducibility of the results. There are some exceptions to open sharing that FARCLIMATE partners should consider when evaluating this mandate. Specifically:

- The obligation to protect results due to legitimate interests or other constraints, such as exploitation, confidentiality, trade secrets or intellectual property rights (IPR).
- Ethical and security considerations.
- Data protection and participant privacy.
- Data too large to be feasibly hosted by an open-access repository.
- Data under license or provided by a third party.

Open access does not affect the decision to exploit research results commercially, e.g. through patenting. The decision on whether to publish through open access must come after the more general decision on whether to publish directly or to first seek protection. In addition, **open access requirements do not imply an obligation to publish results**: The decision to publish is entirely up to the grant beneficiaries. Open access becomes an issue only if publication is chosen as a means of dissemination.

2.1 Data management process

The general principles for the data management process are the following:

- **Involving all relevant knowledge actors:** An essential aspect of FARCLIMATE is the stakeholders' involvement since the beginning of the project to gather data and information and make tailor-made plans and actions. Specifically, FARCLIMATE partners will create focus groups and other co-creation activities under the umbrella of the living labs and the stakeholder management strategy (WP2) to develop policy and other recommendations on climate-resilient societies.
- **Informed consent:** Prior to any interview, survey or other participative activity in which data is collected and following D1.4 indications, all participants involved will be informed about the use of this information, including data sharing, and a consent form will be provided for signature.
- **Data access and sharing:** By default, research and other project data are restricted to the consortium for the execution of project activities. Open sharing of data or documentation with third parties only occurs after a thorough evaluation or preparation process. This approach facilitates the advancement of project activities and aligns with the goals and mandates of open science and dissemination and the need for data protection. Such restricted access would only be granted to consortium-external parties with the informed consent of the research subjects, as established in D1.4. Ethical or legal issues that could impact data sharing include the presence of confidential third-party data and personal data that cannot be anonymized. The identification of these issues will be part of the dataset evaluation process, with clarifications provided on how ownership may affect data sharing and access. **The sharing of sensitive data will be governed by the principles established in D1.4 and this deliverable and may be subject to specific data-sharing agreements if deemed necessary.**
- **General measures to ensure reproducibility of research outputs:**
 - FARCLIMATE partners will ensure that the scientific community and policy makers obtain the same results as the originators of specific findings and will contribute to fewer duplication efforts and false baselines.
 - Transparent research design, robust statistical analyses, addressing negative results, early sharing through preprints, research data and model.
 - Protocols and methods will be shared to minimise variability due to human errors and ensure replicability during the project and afterwards.
- **Managing diverse data outputs:** The types of data and research output generated during the FARCLIMATE project are expected to be in the form of notebooks and logs; tabular data and databases; and documented methodologies and workflows. How these data will be managed will depend on the nature and treatment of the information.
- **Quality assurance processes:** To ensure the accuracy, precision and reliability of the data, FARCLIMATE will involve meticulous data verification and validation techniques, and will be applied consistently across all data categories.
- **Review and update of the data management plan** to reflect important changes due to the inclusion of new datasets, changes in consortium policies or any other external factors. A final version of the DMP (D1.3) will be released by M48.

General approach for making data and information open:

- FARCLIMATE will use OpenAIRE's **Zenodo platform¹ as the primary choice for depositing open data.** Zenodo is a popular repository for making Horizon Europe projects data and publications open and provides easy functionalities for making them FAIR.
- Additionally, other trusted repositories could also be used. In this sense, repositories endorsed by the research communities in the fields of the data or publication are also recommended. *OpenAire Explore²* and *Open Research Europe-approved repositories³* are useful sources for identifying trusted repositories.
- The different publications of FARCLIMATE should also be **published on the FARCLIMATE website and CORDIS in line with the FAIR principles.**

For any additional data-sharing needs, a request should be submitted to the project manager. This request should include the following information:

- *Name of the partner requesting to share data; Name of the third-party organisation with which the partner plans to share the data; Date of request.*
- *Description of data requested and purpose of sharing. Why is sharing 'necessary'?*
- *Will the partner and the third party have a data-sharing agreement in place?*
- *Lawful basis for sharing – please state which.*
- *Are additional conditions met for special categories data?*
- *What are the personal or sensitive information considerations? Was this data sharing stated in the informed consent of the subjects? What arrangements are there for complying with personal and sensitive information rights?*
- *What are the security considerations?*

2.2 Making data findable

Publishing in **Zenodo helps to make data findable^{4,5}**:

- *"(Meta)data are assigned a globally unique and persistent identifier*
 - *A DOI is issued to every published record on Zenodo.*
- *Data are described with rich metadata [defined in reusability below]*
 - *Zenodo's metadata is compliant with DataCite's Metadata Schema minimum and recommended terms, with a few additional enrichments.*
- *Metadata clearly and explicitly include the identifier of the data it describes*
 - *The DOI is a top-level and a mandatory field in the metadata of each record.*
- *(Meta)data are registered or indexed in a searchable resource*
 - *Metadata of each record is indexed and searchable directly in Zenodo's search engine immediately after publishing.*
 - *Metadata of each record is sent to DataCite servers during DOI registration and indexed there."*

¹ <https://zenodo.org>

² <https://explore.openaire.eu/search/content-providers>

³ <https://open-research-europe.ec.europa.eu/for-authors/data-guidelines#approvedrepositories>

⁴ <https://about.zenodo.org/principles>

⁵ <https://help.zenodo.org/docs/deposit/about-records>

Additional general considerations regarding findability:

- **Metadata:** It is recommended to make use of Zenodo (or other repositories) functionalities to edit metadata of the data and documents deposited on the site.
- **Keywords:** Besides descriptive and informative keywords about the publication, it is important to use keywords to optimise its reuse by interested stakeholders. With that in mind, it is recommended to consult classifications such as the general OECD's Fields of Research and Development or UNESCO Nomenclature, or more specific classifications (e.g., the EU Taxonomy for sustainable activities or NACE for economic activities).
- FARCLIMATE's publications on other sites, such as CORDIS and the FARCLIMATE webpage, will be reviewed to ensure they are findable.

2.3 Making data accessible

Publishing in **Zenodo helps to make data accessible**^{4,5}:

- *“(Meta)data are retrievable by their identifier using a standardised communication protocol*
 - *Metadata for individual records as well as record collections are harvestable using the OAI-PMH protocol by the record identifier and the collection name.*
 - *Metadata is also retrievable through the public REST API.*
- *The protocol is open, free, and universally implementable*
 - *See [the first point]. OAI-PMH and REST are open, free and universal protocols for information retrieval on the web.*
- *The protocol allows for an authentication and authorisation procedure, where necessary*
 - *Metadata are publicly accessible and licensed under public domain. No authorization is ever necessary to retrieve it.*
- *Metadata are accessible, even when the data are no longer available*
 - *Data and metadata will be retained for the lifetime of the repository. This is currently the lifetime of the host laboratory CERN, which currently has an experimental programme defined for the next 20 years at least.*
 - *Metadata are stored in high-availability database servers at CERN, which are separate to the data itself.”*

Additional general considerations regarding accessibility:

- As mentioned, the approach for making data and publications accessible is to **publish them in Zenodo, other relevant repositories, FARCLIMATE's web, and CORDIS**.
- FARCLIMATE's publications on other sites, such as CORDIS and the FARCLIMATE webpage, will be reviewed to ensure they are accessible.
- When uploading a dataset or document, providing as much information as possible is always a good practice to make the dataset easily findable.
 - The basic metadata elements that should be provided are the title, publication date, authors, resource type and file format, keywords, funding, license, access rights, data source, data collection methods, data analysis method, DOI (if it exists) and other related identifiers.
- For *datasets developed for research*, important metadata elements are data types, the context of the research (e.g., location, time period), description of data quality assurance and ethics approval (if applicable).

- For *quantitative data*, relevant metadata elements are a variable list, units of measurement, information about missing data, summary statistics and description of data cleaning or transformation.
- For *qualitative data* useful metadata are list of themes/codes that emerged from the analysis, characteristics of participants and how they were recruited, the research context.
- For *geospatial data*, it is relevant metadata regarding spatial data organisation, spatial reference systems, geographic extent, projection and attribute label and domain values.

2.4 Making data interoperable

Publishing in **Zenodo helps to make data interoperable**^{4,5}:

- *“(Meta)data use a formal, accessible, shared, and broadly applicable language for knowledge representation.*
 - *Zenodo uses JSON Schema as internal representation of metadata and offers export to other popular formats such as Dublin Core or MARCXML.*
- *(Meta)data use vocabularies that follow FAIR principles*
 - *For certain terms we refer to open, external vocabularies, e.g.: license (Open Definition), funders (FundRef) and grants (OpenAIRE).*
- *(Meta)data include qualified references to other (meta)data*
 - *Each referenced external piece of metadata is qualified by a resolvable URL.”*

Additional general considerations regarding interoperability:

- **Data, publications and other outputs produced will rely on common formats and standards, community-agreed schemas**, controlled vocabularies or keywords where possible to be interoperable and be integrated with other data and applications. Most of the data in the project that could be openly shared will be textual or tabular; as such, they can be shared in standard formats (e.g., .docx, .xlsx, .pdf), with open-source tools facilitating their accessibility. If, during the project, the need arises to use customised data formats, appropriate sharing mechanisms will be defined.
- FARCLIMATE's publications on other sites, such as CORDIS and the FARCLIMATE webpage, will be reviewed to ensure they are interoperable.

2.5 Increase data reuse

Publishing in **Zenodo helps to make data reusable**^{4,5}:

- *“(Meta)data are richly described with a plurality of accurate and relevant attributes*
 - *Each record contains a minimum of DataCite's mandatory terms, with optionally additional DataCite recommended terms and Zenodo's enrichments.*
- *(Meta)data are released with a clear and accessible data usage license*
 - *License is one of the mandatory terms in Zenodo's metadata and is referring to an Open Definition license.*
 - *Data downloaded by the users is subject to the license specified in the metadata by the uploader.*
- *(Meta)data are associated with detailed provenance*
 - *All data and metadata uploaded is traceable to a registered Zenodo user.*
 - *Metadata can optionally describe the original authors of the published work.*

- *(Meta)data meet domain-relevant community standards*
 - *Zenodo is not a domain-specific repository, yet through compliance with DataCite's Metadata Schema, metadata meets one of the broadest cross-domain standards available."*

Additional general considerations regarding data reuse:

- **FARCLIMATE will publish openly available data and publications under different Creative Commons licenses⁶.** Making data and information available for reuse ensures interested stakeholders, beyond project partners, can benefit from FARCLIMATE results, contributing towards maximising the impact of the project. As such, where possible, FARCLIMATE will facilitate the reusability of its research outputs by relying on licenses for data sharing and reuse (e.g., Creative Commons, Open Data Commons). While the precise details vary, three conditions are commonly found in licences, which are attribution, non-derivative, and non-commerciality.
- FARCLIMATE's publications on other sites, such as CORDIS and the FARCLIMATE webpage, will be reviewed to ensure they are reusable.

2.6 Ethical issues

Data management and open publication shall align with the ethical issues detailed in deliverable *D1.4 Ethical Assessment*.

2.7 Data security

In addition to the FAIR principles to govern the open science data strategy of the project, **the other major principles of FARCLIMATE DMP concern security:** (1) confidentiality of personal and other sensitive data and (2) the integrity and availability of the data and information systems of the project.

FARCLIMATE partners should take **special care of datasets and documents that contain personal or sensitive information**. These particularities are detailed in Section 4.

The key information systems managed by FARCLIMATE partners are:

- The consortium's internal workspace in Teams (managed by UVIGO, WP1). The particularities of this workspace are detailed in Sections 3 and 4.
- The different websites that will use FARCLIMATE (Section 31 provides some considerations regarding these sites):
 - The project website (managed by CTA, WP8).
 - The Transformation Hub (public knowledge platform managed by INV, WP7).
 - The online training platform (managed by C4G, WP4).
- Other information systems employed internally by the partners to collect, store or process data related to the project. See the subsection below on responsibilities.

⁶ <https://creativecommons.org/share-your-work/ccllicenses/> provides a brief description of the most common Creative Commons licenses (including those that we suggest in this document)

2.8 Data management responsibilities

All partners are responsible for managing project data, documentation and publications—and for supporting other partners in this activity. FARCLIMATE consortium members must follow the measures established in this DMP.

All project partners are tasked with collecting, digitalising, anonymising, storing, destroying, and processing data for the specific purpose of the activity in which it has been collected or generated. **The partners collecting, storing and processing the data during their own activity will remain responsible for this data.**

Partners are responsible for:

- Appropriately collecting the necessary consent for processing data.
- Ensuring that data management and informed consent are adequately adjusted to local specificities and regulations.
- Ensuring data management is in line with the plan documented in this deliverable, both in the project's internal and external repositories.
- Preparing the datasets or documents they have generated for their open publication, in line with the FAIR principles and the indications provided in this deliverable.
- Performing quality checks to assess and maintain the quality of datasets and publications.

The project coordinator (PC), UVIGO, is responsible for overall data management in the FARCLIMATE project, including the elaboration of the DMP and its updates. The PC will consult WP leaders, task leaders and responsible partners to determine whether, how and when data and results of the project are shared and become openly available.

The leaders of each WP decide how data, documentation and publications are managed at the WP level. They are responsible for coordinating any data processing activities performed in their WP.

Leaders of each task decide how data, documentation and publications are managed at the task level. They are responsible for coordinating any data processing activities performed in their task.

2.9 Long-term preservation

The value of long-term preservations of the project documents and datasets will be evaluated. This evaluation will be done during their preparation for open publication for datasets and publications from research or aimed at open publication. Other internal documents and information will be assessed by the end of the project, to evaluate the value, the needs and the legal considerations regarding their 5-year preservation and longer preservation. Once that evaluation is done, the consortium will detail specific plans, methods, timelines and roles and responsibilities for preservation. Should they exist, special consideration will be given to those documents and datasets that cannot be published openly or stored in the internal repository.

The measures for making data FAIR (e.g., publication in open repositories, standard data formats, metadata) and data security measures also support the long-term preservation of information.

2.10 Costs of data management

The cost of the internal repository and its 5-year preservation is the responsibility of UVIGO. The costs for hosting and 5-year preservation are the responsibility of the partners who own said results. The use of Zenodo and other open research repositories is free. In order to pursue scientific publications in peer-reviewed indexed journals, partners will take advantage of their transformative agreements with publishers. If the need for funding publication, tools or datasets arises, the project consortium will explore the budgetary possibilities. Website-related costs represent 8.500€. Costs related to data collection are the following: Access to databases and database creation (37.000€, WP3); sensorisation kit (56.000€, WP5); Contracting an organisation for data collecting in several countries (30.000€, WP3).

3 Internal project data and documentation

3.1 Data summary

During FARCLIMATE, consortium partners will produce multiple documents and other data for internal purposes (project management and activity execution). Some are only needed for short periods of time, while others will be valuable until the end of the project or even longer. Consortium data comprises data from project partners. It involves data related to administration, management and project execution within the consortium. This data and documentation will be collected in all WPs.

The **origin of the data** is primarily from the following sources:

- FARCLIMATE partners.
- Stakeholders participating in the living labs of the case study.
- Other stakeholders of the projects.

The main **users** of this internal data are the FARCLIMATE partners.

Table 1. Types of internal project data and documentation

Description	WP	Type	OA Conditions	Format
Internal project management and activity execution data and documentation, without personal or sensitive information.	All	Multiple types, Internal	Public deliverables of the project may include some of this information if deemed relevant for the purpose of the deliverable.	.docx, .xlsx, .pptx, .pdf and other office productivity formats deemed necessary
Project, WP and task KPIs and metrics for monitoring or reporting the progress of the project.	All	Quantitative, Checklist		
KPIs and metrics for monitoring the progress of case studies, their living labs and their activities.	WP2-WP5			

3.2 Data management process

As established in *D1.1 Project Management Guidelines*, it is vital that the partners follow document management procedures to enable users to find and identify relevant files and to ensure version control. Namely:

- **Data collection:** Internal gathering and monitoring of data, information and documentation in WP1 for overall project management but also in the other WPs regarding their tasks.
- **Data processing:** Project documentation will be created as a result of tracking and validating project progress by the project boards, within WP1, for overall project management but also in the other WPs regarding their tasks.

As established in *D1.1 Project Management Guidelines*, **document templates** will be produced using a standard format, including defined styles, page layouts and content structure. CTA prepared these templates at the beginning of the project and are available in the FARCLIMATE (Teams) internal repository. Templates have been produced for deliverables, meeting signatures, and meeting minutes in Microsoft Word .docx format, and for presentations in Microsoft PowerPoint .pptx format. These templates must be used for all project documents. These templates may be updated as the project progresses. Thus, partners must download the most up-to-date version from the repository.

3.3 Making data findable

As established in *D1.1 Project Management Guidelines*, internal data stored in the project's Team repository follows the WP/Task structure to facilitate findability.

Each document will use a structured file name. This method of document coding produces a unique reference for all FARCLIMATE documents stored on the Teams repository.

Documents must be structured using the following format:

- Minutes from meetings will include the meeting date (in the format **YYYY_MM_DD**). For example, "*FARCLIMATE_Minutes_2023_11_30.docx*".
- Deliverables: **FARCLIMATE_WP[WP NUMBER]_[DOCUMENT TYPE AND REFERENCE]_v[VERSION NUMBER]_[STATUS(draft/final)]**. One example of this coding is "*FARCLIMATE_WP5_D5.2_v1_Final.pdf*".

Metadata in Teams: Files stored in Teams contain metadata in a format compatible with Microsoft SharePoint. Many categories, such as tags or content types, can be edited through the file contextual menu "Properties", should the partners need to use metadata for internal purposes.

3.4 Making data accessible

Repository: As established in *D1.1 Project Management Guidelines*, the documents generated in FARCLIMATE will be stored in the **common Teams Group** created specifically for this project.

The partners will upload documents to Teams or send them to the coordinator. WP-specific channels will be made available by WP leaders on Teams to share relevant information within each WP and to share living documents.

At least each channel will count with the following folders:

- A folder for each deliverable of the WP with two subfolders, one for drafts and another for final documents.
- A folder for documents related to meetings of the WP.

Relevant datasets or internally produced documents may be uploaded to the website by the partners themselves, the coordinator or the WP8 leader. The **PC will submit all the final deliverables to the project's Continuous Report portal** of the European Commission. **This process may involve preparing the data for open access** (detailed in Section 8).

Documents generated during the project and raw and processed data will be **retained in the project's repository for 5 years after its end**. UVIGO is responsible for this retention. After the expiry date of the retention period, and unless further legitimate grounds for retention arise, partners are obliged to dispose of personal data securely.

3.5 Making data interoperable

UVIGO and WP leaders will ensure the standards for all datasets, software use, file exchange protocols, etc., use **standard formats** so all partners can operate the resulting data without losing information.

3.6 Ethical, legal or compliance issues

No particular ethical, legal or compliance matters beyond what is established in *D1.4 Ethical Assessment*.

3.7 Data security

The Teams repository offers the following security features:

- All data in Teams is encrypted, both at rest and in transit.
- Support of advanced sign-on and authentication such as multi-factor authentication and single sign-on.
- Secure guest access.
- Teams has built-in and up-to-date measures to handle common security threats.
- Teams allows for the management of devices and apps to ensure security.
- Teams is compliant with various standards and regulations, ensuring data privacy and security.

Also, to minimise the consequences of potential data losses, the **data will be backed up** at regular time intervals based on change frequency and criticality.

In addition, **all project partners are expected to process data using appropriate means** (such as private servers or cloud service providers) that adhere to the relevant legal data protection requirements (e.g., GDPR). The partners must ensure that this data is protected, and necessary data security controls have been implemented to minimise the risk of information leak and destruction.

Access to closed data will only be permitted to authorised project partners. In case of a data breach, the responsible project partner will notify its competent national supervisory authority (e.g., data protection authority) and the data subject(s) that may be affected by the breach without undue delay and, where feasible, not later than 72 hours after becoming aware of the breach. The responsible partner will document any personal data breaches, including information such as the facts relevant to the breach, its effects and the remedial action(s) taken.

4 Internal data and documentation with personal and sensitive information

4.1 Data summary

This is a subcategory of internal data and documentation described in the previous section. The main difference is that it refers **to internal data and documents containing personal and sensitive information that require additional care and security.**

Personal data refers to information relating to an identified or identifiable natural person. Article 4(1) of Regulation (EU) 2016/679 (GDPR) states that *“personal data’ means any information relating to an identified or identifiable natural person (‘data subject’); an identifiable natural person is one who can be identified, directly or indirectly, in particular by reference to an identifier such as a name, an identification number, location data, an online identifier or to one or more factors specific to the physical, physiological, genetic, mental, economic, cultural or social identity of that natural person”.*

Other sensitive data includes:

- **Intellectual property.** FARCLIMATE intellectual property (IP) management follows the IAPED approach (identify, assess, protect, exploit and disseminate). At the proposal stage, FARCLIMATE identified the intellectual property interests of the consortium members and access rights within the project. During the project, the assessment and protection of intellectual property rights (IPR) will be addressed by task T8.4 (exploitation activities) and supervised by the Innovation and Exploitation Board (defined in *D1.1 Project Management Guidelines*).
- **Legal persons and organisations.** Our activities also collect identifiable data of organisations.

Origin of the data: The consortium will collect common personal data, e.g., name and professional contact information, location or interviews.

The **users** of this internal data are the FARCLIMATE partners, strictly for the activities consented to by the person. The use of personal data is envisaged for tasks dealing with stakeholder engagement, co-creation activities, living labs, workshops, consumer behavioural assessments, training, the creation of demonstrative stands and brigades, etc.

Table 2. Types of internal project data and documentation with personal and sensitive information

Description	WP	Type	Format
Personal or sensitive information of FARCLIMATE partners and people working on the project	All	Multiple types, Internal, Personal, sensitive	.docx, .xlsx, .pptx, .pdf and other office productivity formats deemed necessary
Personal or sensitive information of people from FARCLIMATE case studies			
Personal or sensitive information of people or entities outside the consortium and case studies			

4.2 Data management process

Data collection: In activities where personal information is gathered and stored, FARCLIMATE partners must pay special attention to privacy, data protection and data management. **Information and data that includes personal or sensitive information shall be gathered in accordance with the procedures of informed consent.** *D1.4 Ethical Assessment* details the informed consent procedure and provides a template for the information sheet and the informed consent form.

Nonetheless, partners can use their own information sheets and informed consent forms if they comply with the principles stated here and GDPR and provide information about the FARCLIMATE project, the project logo and the funder's logos.

Data processing: Whenever the consortium needs to process personal data, they will do so **in compliance with applicable GDPR and national law on data protection** (including authorisations or notification requirements). Art. 5 of the GDPR defines the following main principles regarding the processing of personal data: (a) lawfulness, fairness, and transparency; (b) purpose limitation; (c) data minimisation; (d) accuracy; (e) storage limitation; (f) integrity and confidentiality; and (g) accountability.

Beyond the management of the datasets and information systems, the use of the personal data gathered in FARCLIMATE must commit to the following principles:

- Personal data must be used in accordance with the informed consent given by the participant and the rights they have regarding their data.
- Wherever possible, personal data must be processed anonymously or pseudonymously. Data and research outputs will be anonymised before being made accessible to third parties.
- Personal data must be processed only if it is genuinely adequate, relevant and limited to what is necessary for the project (data minimisation principle).
- Using personal data and images/video for communication purposes will require specific authorisation, documented in a specific clause in the informed consent form.

Dissemination and communication lists shall also ensure compliance with the protection of personal data and adequate security.

4.3 Making data findable, accessible, interoperable and reusable

It follows the procedures for internal data and documentation established in the Section 3, taking into consideration the special security, protection and usage of this type of personal and sensitive data.

4.4 Ethical, legal or compliance issues

Besides the general ethical, legal or compliance issues established in *D1.4 Ethical Assessment*, we highlight the following considerations in D1.4:

- To comply with GDPR and national data protection laws, the processing of personal data in FARCLIMATE shall adhere to the following principles: Fairness, Transparency, Accountability, Data quality, Confidentiality and Security.
- One partner of FARCLIMATE belongs to a non-EU country: UICN (Switzerland). It is not planned to import or export anything but data between EU countries and Switzerland. Regarding this, the European Commission, on the basis of Art. 45 of *Regulation (EU) 2016/679 (GDPR)*, has determined that Switzerland has an adequate level of data protection (*Commission Decision 2000/518/EC* and reviewed in 2024 [*Document SWD (2024) 3 final*]) and, thus, personal data can flow from the EU to that third country without any further safeguard being necessary. Additionally, the activities carried out by UICN (research and technical assistance in Nature-based solutions for agriculture, forestry and fishing) are allowed in other EU countries.

4.5 Data security

In addition to the security aspects established for the internal repository in Section 3.7, we highlight the following considerations:

- **Personal data collection, storage, modification, retrieval, transmission and elimination must be subject to appropriate safeguards.** In addition, the level of data security must be appropriate to the risk for the participants in case of disclosure.
- Sensitive data should be managed by its respective owners/users to the maximum extent possible and should never be uploaded to the shared project data space.

5 Reused datasets and information

5.1 Data summary

During FARCLIMATE, consortium partners may reuse existing data to conduct research, innovation, and living-lab development activities.

The **origin** of the data will be public and open data repositories and data from commercial databases will also be obtained (e.g., for financial and business information).

The main **users** of this internal data are the FARCLIMATE partners.

Table 3. Types of reused datasets and information

Description	WP	Type	Format
Public databases with environmental and socioeconomic information at NUTS3 level for geospatial analysis of European regions.	WP2	Quantitative	Tabular formats, .csv, .xls, .xlsx, SQL
Databases (e.g., ecoinvent, Eurostat or dat.Europe) with information on global value chains resulting from scientific research.	WP3		
Access to databases with primary information on entrepreneurship, investments, new activities and new value chain actors.			
Previous projects, studies and relevant research papers analysing the functioning and evolution of global value chains resulting from scientific research.	WP4	Multiple types	.docx, .xlsx, .pptx, .pdf and other office productivity formats.
Existing educational material related to climate change adaptation that had been used by the partners in prior activities.			
Knowledge on existing current adaptation platforms (e.g., Climate ADAPT, A-PLAT, GCA Knowledge Exchange), as well as previous initiatives and projects (e.g. UNaLab and Score projects) for curating a portfolio of innovative transformational solutions.	WP7		Tabular formats, .csv, .xls, .xlsx, SQL

5.2 Data management process

Integrated into the data management process of other activities (see Sections 6-8).

5.3 Making data findable

A **data statement** should be included at the end of articles or other publications, before the reference list, describing each dataset and including a link to the relevant repository and the dataset's persistent identifier. When drafting the statement, please include the name of the repository used and a brief description of the contents of each dataset.

5.4 Ethical, legal or compliance issues

Besides the ethical, legal or compliance matters established in *D1.4 Ethical Assessment*, clear agreements are needed for reusing non-open data from other sources. These should detail access, use, and redistribution terms, including any obligations like citation.

5.5 Data security

No particular security matters beyond what is established in Section 2.

6 Datasets for open publication

6.1 Data summary

During FARCLIMATE, consortium partners will gather quantitative and qualitative data, or a combination of both, for the purpose of conducting their research, innovation and living-lab development activities.

The **origin of the data** is primarily from stakeholders participating in the case study’s living labs, although other stakeholders of the project may contribute.

The main **users** of this internal data are the FARCLIMATE partners. However, many of the datasets that will be produced will have potential reuse value for researchers, students, analysts, policy makers and other people interested in data related to climate change adaptation. In this sense, FARCLIMATE will seek to contribute data to relevant initiatives within the context of the Climate Change Adaptation Mission.

Table 4. Datasets with potential for open publication

Description	WP	Type	OA Conditions	Format
Geoprocessed evaluation of environmental impact of climate change in NUTS3 European regions.	WP2	Quantitative, geospatial, Evaluation from criteria.		.csv, .shp and .png.
Data collected from the case studies with research value regarding identification or classification of regional and sectoral stakeholders—in the context of climate change adaptation in the fishery, forestry and agriculture sectors in the case study regions.	WP2, WP3, WP5	Multiple types: Quantitative and qualitative. Gathered through interviews, focus groups, surveys, ...	To be evaluated, Anonymisation	Internally, at discretion of the needs of the partners but favouring common standards. Data made open will be transformed to more open format if necessary.
Data collected from the case studies with research value regarding co-creation, living-labs, stakeholder engagement and current social innovation—in the context of climate change adaptation in the fishery, forestry and agriculture sectors in the case study regions.	WP2			
Data collected from the case studies with research value regarding value chains, sectors, socioeconomic factors and environmental factors—in the context of climate change adaptation in the fishery, forestry and agriculture sectors in the case study regions.	WP3			
Data from survey to understand consumer acceptance/behaviour towards the transition to climate resilience solutions	WP3	Quantitative (some qualitative), Survey.	Anonymisation	
Data collected from the case studies with research value regarding perception for risks and social and environmental impact in the agriculture sector—in the context of the case study regions.	WP5			
Sensor-based data (e.g., tree, soil, ambient data) from the closer to nature silviculture pilots in different case study regions.	WP5	Quantitative		
State of the art in climate adaptation (entities, projects, platforms, etc.), with emphasis on the European context.	WP7	Tabular		

6.2 Data management process

Data collection and processing: As long as they comply (1) with the ethical and data protection criteria established in this and *D1.4 Ethical Assessment* deliverables and (2) with the data management procedures established in this and *D1.1 Project Handbook* deliverables, the **data collection and processing activities of each task should follow the procedures that those responsible for the tasks consider appropriate from the point of view of the methodology of the activity they are doing.** Internally, it should follow the procedures for internal data and documentation established in Section 3.

In this context, it is **paramount to evaluate data quality** following the standards of the activity's methodological approach, checking for completeness, accuracy, and consistency and identifying any missing values or discrepancies to rectify them.

Data preparation for open publication: Before proceeding to make the data FAIR, the first step is to **evaluate a candidate dataset for open publication**, which involves assessing the following aspects:

- **Dataset relevancy.** Ensure the dataset aligns with broad research objectives and adds value to the scientific community.
- **Reasons for not sharing.** Assess whether the datasets cannot be shared or need to be shared under restricted conditions, explaining why, separating legal, ethical or private reasons from intentional restrictions and legitimate interests or other constraints.
- **Ethical and privacy implications.** Ensure the data respects privacy rights and IPR. If the dataset includes sensitive information, anonymise it to protect identities.
- **Usability of the dataset.** It should be easily understandable and usable by others. Provide clear information on the methodology used for data collection and the meaning of variables.
- Ensure the data is in a suitable **format** for open publication. To increase accessibility, preferably, use non-proprietary and widely accepted formats.

6.3 Making data findable

In addition to the indications in Section 2.2, some data repositories, such as Zenodo, provide functionality which allows the **addition of links to any published articles associated with the dataset.** If possible, we recommend updating metadata in the data repository to include a link (e.g., DOI) to the published article or deliverable related to the dataset.

6.4 Making data accessible

In addition to the indications in Section 2.3, **the data made open will be deposited in the repository at most 3 months after the corresponding publication or deliverable is made openly available** (i.e., the approved version of the deliverable). In general, data generated or collected by the project should be deposited as soon as possible after data production or generation or after adequate processing and quality control have taken place.

6.5 Making data interoperable

In addition to the indications in Section 2.4, where third-party proprietary software has been used, **an open-source alternative must be provided in the article to allow for the replication of the analysis or research by all readers**. Exceptions may be made if the chosen proprietary software performs specific functions and there is no open-source alternative that can carry out these functions in the same manner.

6.6 Increase data reuse

Indications in Section 2.5.

6.7 Ethical, legal or compliance issues

No particular ethical, legal or compliance matters beyond what is established in *D1.4 Ethical Assessment*.

6.8 Data security

For publicly shared data, both the website of the project and the repositories used will ensure proper security and backup mechanisms. For Zenodo, the CERN Data Centre provides sufficient security measures and assurances for the long-term preservation of the results⁷.

⁷ <https://about.zenodo.org/infrastructure>

7 Research publications

7.1 Data summary

At least 15 scientific publications relating to FARCLIMATE results are expected to be published both during the project and following its conclusion in open access, related to the following topics (among others): climate change, climate change adaptation and resilient communities. After depositing publications, partners will ensure their open access via green or golden model.

The **origin** is the research conducted by FARCLIMATE partners using the data and information collected from the case studies and the external reused datasets, described in other sections.

In addition to FARCLIMATE partners and case study stakeholders, the academic community and others interested in the state-of-the-art of climate change adaptation will be among the primary **users** of these research publications.

As Section 16 of the *Horizon Europe Programme Guide* establishes, **all peer-reviewed scientific publications arising from Horizon Europe funding must be made available in open access**. The mandate does not cover non-peer-reviewed publications, but it is a good practice to make them open as well.

FARCLIMATE will focus primarily on publications in high-impact journals with open access options. As an alternative to journals, partners are encouraged to consider publishing in **Open Research Europe**, which will allow to comply with the Open Access EC requirements.

7.2 Data management process

Data collection and processing: As long as they comply (1) with the ethical and data protection criteria established in this and *D1.4 Ethical Assessment* deliverables and (2) with the data management procedures established in this and *D1.1 Project Handbook* deliverables, the **elaboration of the research publications should follow the procedures that those responsible for the involved tasks consider appropriate from the point of view of the methodology of the activity they are doing**. Internally, it should follow the procedures for internal data and documentation established in Section 3.

In this sense, beyond common .docx, .pptx, .pdf or .xlsx formats, it is also recommended to use common practices, tools and formats for academic publishing, such as (among others) latex for producing documentation and bibtex or RIS for bibliography file formats.

7.3 Making data findable

In addition to what is established in Section 2.2, some indications for making data findable are the following:

- Unique and long-lasting references (persistent identifiers) to the publications in the public or institutional repositories (e.g., Zenodo's or journal's DOIs) will be used.
- To enhance the findability of research outputs and their potential reuse, information optimised for findability should be included in the metadata.

7.4 Making data accessible

In addition to the indications in Section 2.3, this subsection contains some indications for making accessible research publications.

7.4.1 Repository

Research publications must be freely and immediately accessible online via a repository. Preprints are expected to be prepared and deposited in open access repositories (mainly Zenodo, but additional trusted scientific repositories such as RePEc, SciELO, arXiv, OSF or ScienceOpen can be used) **as immediately as possible and at the latest at the time of publication** (i.e. note that under Horizon Europe an embargo on open access is no longer accepted). It is also recommended to upload the preprint to the institutional repositories of the partners. Most of these materials will also be freely available on the project website and continuously updated throughout the project duration.

The standard procedure is to upload a copy of the published version or the final peer-reviewed manuscript accepted for publication (i.e. Author Accepted Manuscript - AAM; or author's postprint), with a **CC-BY or equivalent** license for articles (at least for the AAM); or with a **CC BY-NC, CC BY-ND or equivalent** license prohibiting commercial use or derivative works, for monographs and other long texts.

The upload should also include the following information:

- Acronym/code of the project.
- Information about any research outputs, tools or instruments necessary to substantiate the conclusions of the scientific publication.

7.4.2 Retention of copyright

It is also required that **authors retain copyright** to meet Horizon Europe requirements. This condition is met if:

- The authors have signed a Copyright Transfer Agreement, but the publisher allows for the AAM or the Version of Record to be uploaded to a repository.
- The authors retain the copyright to the published article.

Authors may need to interact with prospective publishers or apply the Rights Retention Strategy outlined by Coalition S⁸.

If publishing in a hybrid journal, costs may be covered by a transformative agreement between the corresponding author institution and the publisher. Under Horizon Europe, so-called '**transformative journals**' are considered ordinary hybrid journals and publishing fees are not eligible costs.

⁸ <https://www.coalition-s.org/rights-retention-strategy>

7.4.3 Open access under Horizon Europe

Under Horizon Europe, open access can be achieved in two ways:

- Deposit the publication in an **open access repository** for scientific publications.
- Publish the research in an **open access journal** or publication. Even in this case, it is necessary to deposit the publication in a repository.

The following graphic explains the process:

Figure 1. Horizon Europe Open Access Mandate. The upper path represents **gold open access** (publishing in an open access journal), the intermediate path represents **green open access** (publishing in a subscription journal) and the lower path represents **hybrid open access** (publishing in a hybrid journal). Image: England & Malaguarnera, 2022 (CC-BY 4.0)⁹.

7.4.4 Metadata

Metadata of deposited publications must be open under a **CC 0 or equivalent**, in line with the FAIR principles (in particular machine-actionable) and provide information at least about the following:

- Author(s), title, date of publication, publication venue.
- Horizon Europe funding, grant project name, acronym and number.
- licensing terms.
- a persistent identifier for the publication.

⁹ <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7324364>

7.5 Making data interoperable

In addition to the indications in Section 2.4, where third-party proprietary software has been used, **an open-source alternative must be provided in the article to allow for the replication of the analysis or research by all readers**. Exceptions may be made if the chosen proprietary software performs specific functions and there is no open-source alternative that can carry out these functions in the same manner.

7.6 Increase data reuse

In addition to the indications in Section 2.5, for replicability purposes, all **articles should include details of any software and code** that are required to view the datasets described or to replicate the analysis. Authors should state the version, details of where the software can be accessed, and any variable parameters that could impact the outcome of the results. If authors have coded software in-house, the source code should be written in (or be compatible with) an open-source programming language and should be archived under an open license (preferably an OSI-approved license or CC-BY 4.0) and shared. For code stored in GitHub or equivalent code repositories, authors should create a 'public registration' for the project to obtain a DOI. **Information about software should be included in a software availability statement**, which can be added at the end of the article, before the references list.

7.7 Ethical, legal or compliance issues

No particular ethical, legal or compliance matters beyond what is established in *D1.4 Ethical Assessment*.

7.8 Data security

For publicly shared publications, both the website of the project and the repositories used will ensure proper security and backup mechanisms. For Zenodo, the CERN Data Centre provides sufficient security measures and assurances for the long-term preservation of the publications⁷.

8 Other information and documents with reuse value

8.1 Data summary

During FARCLIMATE, consortium partners will produce diverse information about the project that will be documented in the project deliverables. The purpose of this information is to describe the **plans and methodologies of FARCLIMATE** for conducting the project activities, as well as **assessments, analysis and insights** into the different topics covered by the project. One of the major informative results of FARCLIMATE are **stakeholder-focused recommendations** such as policies, plans and strategies. The purpose is to provide new responses to the disruptive change associated with climate change. Finally, various materials will be produced and published for **dissemination** purposes.

The **origin** of this information is the activities conducted by FARCLIMATE partners using the data and information collected from the case studies and the external reused datasets, described in other sections.

Besides FARCLIMATE partners and case study stakeholders, many types of **users** might be interested in this information. Namely, policy makers and stakeholders involved in local development and climate change adaptation or other European research and innovation projects. Additionally, dissemination materials will have a special focus on the general public, especially the local public at the case studies.

8.2 Data management process

Data collection and processing: As long as they comply (1) with the ethical and data protection criteria established in this and *D1.4 Ethical Assessment* deliverables and (2) with the data management procedures established in this and *D1.1 Project Handbook* deliverables, the **elaboration of the information and documents should follow the procedures that those responsible for the tasks consider appropriate from the point of view of the methodology of the activity they are doing**. Internally, it follows the procedures for internal data and documentation established in Section 3.

In this sense, beyond common .docx, .pptx, .pdf or .xlsx formats, it is also recommended to adhere to common practices, tools and formats pertinent to the specific field. If possible, it is preferable to use open tools and formats.

8.3 Making data findable

In addition to what is established in Section 2.2, some indications for making data findable are the following:

- **All FARCLIMATE deliverables will be identifiable based on a common naming convention** established in the proposal. Version control will be clearly identified and will follow the version control set out in *D1.1 Project Handbook*.
- Unique and long-lasting references (persistent identifiers) to the documents in the public or institutional repositories (e.g., Zenodo's or CORDIS' DOIs) will be used. Information optimised for findability should be included in the metadata to enhance the findability of research outputs and their potential reuse.

8.4 Making data accessible

In addition to the indications in Section 2.3, deliverables will be published on Zenodo, CORDIS and FARCLIMATE websites. Additionally, most of these materials will also be freely available on the project website and continuously updated throughout the project duration.

8.5 Making data interoperable

No additional indication beyond what is indicated in Section 2.4.

8.6 Increase data reuse

No additional indication beyond what is indicated in Section 2.4.

8.7 Ethical, legal or compliance issues

No particular ethical, legal or compliance matters beyond what is established in *D1.4 Ethical Assessment*.

8.8 Data security

For publicly shared publications, both the website of the project and the repositories used will ensure proper security and backup mechanisms. For Zenodo, the CERN Data Centre provides sufficient security measures and assurances for the long-term preservation of the publications⁷.

9 Online sites

9.1 Data summary

FARCLIMATE will create or set up several online sites during the project.

The **origin** of the data used in the sites is varied. First, data and information produced in FARCLIMATE that will feed the sites, properly curated for making relevant information FAIR and complying with personal information protection. Second, the site data itself, which will include user information. Third, additional dissemination or training materials incorporated into the sites but not produced by FARCLIMATE.

In addition to FARCLIMATE partners and case study stakeholders, various types of users may be interested in this information. These include policy makers, stakeholders involved in local development and climate change adaptation, as well as participants in other European research and innovation projects. Moreover, special emphasis will be placed on disseminating materials to the general public, particularly the local public in the case studies

Table 5. Types of reused datasets and information

Description	WP
Educational platform	WP4
Transformation Hub (online knowledge platform)	WP7
FARCLIMATE website	WP8

Details on data management are subject to the design and technologies used to implement the sites and will be provided in their corresponding deliverables: *D4.2 Training Online Platform*, due in M20 (May 2025) and Transformation Hub deliverables (*D7.1 Platform Content Strategy and Experience Insights* and *D7.2 Platform Documentation*, due in September 2024 and September 2025 respectively).

Nonetheless, FARCLIMATE sites must be in line (1) with the ethical and data protection criteria established in this and *D1.4 Ethical Assessment* deliverables and (2) with the data management procedures established in this and *D1.1 Project Handbook* deliverables.

References

Directive (EU) 2019/1024 of the European Parliament and of the Council of 20 June 2019 on open data and the re-use of public sector information (recast).

<http://data.europa.eu/eli/dir/2019/1024/oj>

European Commission (2022) *EU Grants: Data management plan (HE):V1.1.*

https://ec.europa.eu/info/funding-tenders/opportunities/docs/2021-2027/horizon/temp-form/report/data-management-plan_he_en.docx

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Organisation for Economic Co-operation and Development (2015). *Frascati Manual 2015: Guidelines for Collecting and Reporting Data on Research and Experimental Development.*

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Regulation (EC) No 1893/2006 of the European Parliament and of the Council of 20 December 2006 establishing the statistical classification of economic activities NACE Revision 2 and amending Council Regulation (EEC) No 3037/90 as well as certain EC Regulations on specific statistical domains (Text with EEA relevance).

<http://data.europa.eu/eli/reg/2006/1893/oj>

Regulation (EU) 2016/679 of the European Parliament and of the Council of 27 April 2016 on the protection of natural persons with regard to the processing of personal data and on the free movement of such data, and repealing Directive 95/46/EC (General Data Protection Regulation) (Text with EEA relevance).

<http://data.europa.eu/eli/reg/2016/679/oj>

Regulation (EU) 2020/852 of the European Parliament and of the Council of 18 June 2020 on the establishment of a framework to facilitate sustainable investment, and amending Regulation (EU) 2019/2088 (Text with EEA relevance). [EU Taxonomy]

<http://data.europa.eu/eli/reg/2020/852/oj>

Regulation (EU) 2021/695 of the European Parliament and of the Council of 28 April 2021 establishing Horizon Europe – the Framework Programme for Research and Innovation, laying down its rules for participation and dissemination, and repealing Regulations (EU) No 1290/2013 and (EU) No 1291/2013 (Text with EEA relevance).

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